

**Condensation of Cyanacetic Ester with some Aryl
and Alkylamines. Preparation of some
Aryl and Alkyl substituted
Cyanacetamides.**

BY KUVBJI GOSAI NAIK AND YESHWANT NARAYAN BHAT.

The method adopted in the preparation of these compounds was a modification of that employed by Freund (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 134) and Whiteley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 24), in the preparation of malon-diphenylamide.

Cyanacetanilide [*Compt. rend.*, 1895, 121, 189 ; Quenda, *Chem. Centr.*, 1892, i, 383 from *Atti. R. Accad. Sci. Torino*, 27 ; Warapsky and Hillers, *J. pr. Chim.*, (ii), 92, 297], cyanacet-*p*-toluidide (Grothe, *Arch. Pharm.*, 238, 608 ; Haller, *Compt. rend.*, 1889, 108, 1116), cyanacetbenzylamide (Guareschi, *Chem. Centr.*, 1892, i, 382 from *Atti R. Accad. Sci. Torino*, 27) and cyanacetxylylide (m. p. 167°) are already known.

(1) Cyanacet-*o*-toluidide, (2) cyanacet-*m*-toluidide (3) cyanacet- α -naphthylamide, (4) cyanacet- β -naphthylamide, (5) cyanacet-*adj*-*m*-xylylide, (6) cyanacetmethyl-amide and (7) cyanacetethylamide were prepared for the first time. The methods employed had to be varied with the varying basic nature of the amines, more drastic method being employed in the case of those amines which possessed feeble ammoniacal characteristics.

Benzylamine resembles, though remotely, the paraffin amines and hence the method of preparing an amide with the help of this amine has to be modified from that adopted in the previous cases. Aniline, toluidines and naphthylamines possess ammoniacal characteristics to a very feeble extent indeed, and in their cases, more drastic methods for the production of the substituted derivatives were employed. We can thus roughly divide the preparations of the amides into three divisions :—

A. Cyanacetmethylamide; cyanacetethylamide.

B. Cyanacetbenzylamide.

C. Cyanacetanilide ; cyanacet-*p*-toluidide ; cyanacet-*o*-toluidide ; cyanacet-*m*-toluidide ; cyanacet-*a*-naphthylamide ; cyanacet-*β*-naphthylamide ; cyanacet-*adj.*-*m*-xylylide.

Of the above substituted amides, cyanacetanilide, cyanacet-*p*-toluidide and cyanacetbenzylamide are known, but no reliable details of the methods employed in their preparations could be found. The melting points of these substances fairly agree with those reported and the analyses confirm the percentage of nitrogen required.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Substituted Amides of Cyanacetic Ester.

In the preparation of substituted amides of the aromatic series Whiteley's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 24) with the modification described by Naikl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379) was followed.

Cyanacetanilide.—Ethyl cyanacetate (37 g.) and pure redistilled aniline (45 g.) were mixed together in a round-bottomed flask provided with a wide upright bent tube, one end of which passed through a cork in the mouth of the flask, and the other end was attached to the condenser. The flask was kept at 160°—170° for six hours. The height of the upright portion of the bent tube was so adjusted that for every drop of alcohol distilled over, a dozen drops of the liquid went back to the flask. This was to avoid any of the reacting liquids coming over unchanged. The temperature was slowly raised to 180° till no more alcohol came over. The contents of the flask, when hot, were then poured into a porcelain mortar where the whole solidified. The colour of the liquid when taken out of the bath was red. The solid cake was broken and triturated with a mixture of equal volumes of benzene and light petroleum, and filtered at the pump. The process was repeated until the reddish colour of the solid disappeared. The yield was 66 per cent.

Cyanacetanilide is readily soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, ethyl acetate and nitrobenzene ; less readily so in benzene, toluene, chloroform and hot water ; and insoluble in light petroleum (b. p. 50-60°), carbon tetrachloride, carbon disulphide and xylol. It was crystallised from alcohol as white needles,

m. p. 198-199°. (Found: N, 17.68. $C_9H_8N_2O$ requires N, 17.50 per cent.).

Cyanacet-p-toluidide.—Cyanacet-p-toluidide was prepared from ethyl cyanacetate (20 g.) and freshly distilled p-toluidine (21 g.) in the same way as cyanacetanilide.

The white product so obtained is readily soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetic acid, ethyl acetate, acetone and nitrobenzene, less so in benzene, toluene and chloroform; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride and hot water, and insoluble in ether, light petroleum and carbon bisulphide. It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 180°. (Found: N, 15.71. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.).

Cyanacet-o-toluidide.—Ethyl cyanacetate (34 g.) and o-toluidine (29 g.) were condensed together in a similar way.

The white product is readily soluble in benzene, toluene, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, acetic acid, chloroform, acetone and nitrobenzene; less readily so in carbon tetrachloride, very sparingly soluble in hot water and petroleum, and insoluble in carbon bisulphide and ether. It was crystallised from alcohol as thin plates, m. p. 125°. (Found: N, 15.90. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.).

Cyanacet-m-toluidide.—Ethyl cyanacetate (15 g.) and m-toluidine (13 g.) were condensed in the usual manner. The solid was triturated and washed with ether.

It is readily soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetic acid, ethyl acetate, acetone and nitrobenzene; less readily in benzene, toluene, chloroform and hot water; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide and ether; and insoluble in petroleum. It separated from benzene in the form of white needles, m. p. 132°. (Found: N, 16.25. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.).

Cyanacet-a-naphthylamide.—Ethyl cyanacetate (22 g.) and a-naphthylamine (25 g.) were similarly condensed. The product was finally washed with alcohol until the reddish colour of the solid was removed.

It is freely soluble in ethylacetate, acetic acid, acetone, and nitrobenzene; less soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, benzene,

toluene and chloroform; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide, petroleum, ether and hot water. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 175°. (Found: N, 13.65. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

Cyanacet- β -naphthylamide.—Ethyl cyanacetate (25 g.) and β -naphthylamine (22 g.) were condensed as in the previous cases.

The white solid so obtained is very soluble in ethyl acetate, acetic acid, acetone and nitro-benzene; less so, in benzene, toluene, chloroform, hot water and methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide, and ether; and insoluble in light petroleum. It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 174°. (Found: N, 13.18. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 13.88 per cent.).

Cyanacet-adj-m-xylylide.—Ethyl cyanacetate (11 g.) and *adj-m*-xylydine (12 g.) were condensed in the usual manner. The product is readily soluble in ethyl acetate, acetic acid, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and nitrobenzene; less so in benzene, toluene and chloroform and very slightly soluble in petroleum, hot water, carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide and ether. It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 107°. (Found: N, 15.24. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2O$ requires N, 14.89 per cent.).

Cyan-acetbenzylamide.—In the preparation of this substance, Whiteley's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 370) for the preparation of malon-di-benzylamide was used.

Ethyl cyanacetate (22 g.) and benzylamine (22 g.) were put in a conical flask and refluxed gently on a sand-bath. The substance condensed readily to a yellowish white mass. The heating was stopped after seven hours and the solid was washed with a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether to free it from unchanged reactants. The yield was 90 per cent.

It dissolves readily in benzene, toluene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetic acid, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and nitrobenzene; less readily in carbon bisulphide and hot water, and is sparingly soluble in light petroleum, carbon tetrachloride and ether. It was crystallised from benzene in white long needles, m. p. 120°. (Found: N, 16.19. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.).

Cyanacetmethylamide.—This was prepared by a method corresponding to the method of Whiteley (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of

malon-di-ethylamide, by shaking a mixture of ethyl cyanacetate (50 g.) of methylamine (45 g. of 33% solution) and sodium hydroxide (0.2 g.) for about one hour, at 0°, until it was homogeneous. After keeping the mixture at the ordinary temperature for twelve hours the solution was concentrated on a water-bath. On cooling, a reddish pasty mass was obtained. It was drained on a porous plate when a mass of granular solid was obtained. The yield was very poor being about 25 per cent.

It is very soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetic acid, acetone, water and nitrobenzene; less soluble in benzene and toluene; and sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide ether and petroleum. It crystallises in long white needles from benzene, m. p. 101°. (Found: N, 28.85. $C_4H_8N_2O$ requires N, 28.57 per cent.).

Cyanacet-ethylamide.—Ethyl cyanacetate (28 g.) was condensed with ethylamine (33 g. of 33 per cent solution) in the same way as cyanacetmethylamide. The yield was about 15 per cent.

It is readily soluble in chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetic acid, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, water, acetone and nitrobenzene; less readily in benzene and toluene; and sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide, ether and light petroleum. It was crystallised from benzene as white needles, m. p. 74°. (Found: N, 25.21. $C_5H_8N_2O$ requires N, 25.0 per cent.).

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
THE COLLEGE, BARODA.

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